

Synthesis, spectral and thermal studies of copper(II) complexes of azodyes derived from 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-amino-5-pyrazolone

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Abstract : Some novel metal complexes of copper(II) with azodyes derived from 4-aminoantipyrene and *p*-bromophenol have been synthesized and characterized by elemental analysis, IR, UV-Visible and ESR spectra, thermal studies, magnetic and conductance measurements. The X-ray diffraction patterns of the complex [Cu(PBPAAP)(NCS)(Cl)] (where PBPAAP = parabromophenolazoantipyrene) have been examined and were indexed. The results show that the complex belongs to the orthorhombic crystal system with unit cell dimensions : $a = 7.21 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.77 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 12.65 \text{ \AA}$. The ligands are found to behave in a neutral bidentate manner. The X-band ESR spectra of the complex [Cu(PBPAAP)(CH₃COO)₂] shows an axial ligand field symmetry. All the complexes show square planar geometry with magnetic moments ranging from 1.79 to 1.85 B.M.

Keywords : Cu^{II}, azodyes, thermal studies.

Introduction

Copper is an essential element present in all organisms both land and marine, and early literature is rich with investigations concerning the presence of copper in different forms of life¹. In recent years, a great deal of study on the copper(II) complexes has been driven by the hope of modeling biological molecules that contain copper. Since Cu^{II} is susceptible to Jahn-Teller distortion, a regular octahedral complex is never obtained. Instead a tetragonally distorted one is resulted².

The work on the copper derivatives of 2,2'-dicarboxy azobenzene, *o*-carboxybenzene azo-*p*-cresol, *o*-carboxybenzene azo- β -naphthol, azomethine dyes and their pyridine and quinoline adducts are reported. Harikumar Nair *et al.* have reported the synthesis of Cu^{II} complexes with two potential multidentate ligands, 1,2-dihydro-1,5-dimethyl-2-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-methyl-phenyl-azo)-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (cresolazoantipyrene, CAAPH) and 1,2-dihydro-1,5-dimethyl-2-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-chlorophenylazo)-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one (chlorophenolazoantipyrene, CPAAPH)^{3,4}.

The rich chemistry of azo compounds is associated with several important biological reactions such as protein synthesis, carcinogenesis, immuno chemical affinity labeling, nitrogen fixation and many important medical

and industrial uses⁵. Since 4-aminoantipyrene possesses biological activity, the ligand parabromophenolazoantipyrene and its complexes are expected to provide ample scope for the biological studies. Sali Thomas *et al.* have reported the ligand BPAAP, derived from 4-aminoantipyrene and *p*-bromophenol and its oxomolybdenum(V) and dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes⁶.

In view of the importance of copper compounds we have isolated and characterized some new complexes of the ligand 2,3-dimethyl-1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxy-5-bromophenylazo)-pyrazol-5-one (PBPAAP), derived from biologically active molecule, 4-aminoantipyrene. The ligand PBPAAP acts as a potential bidentate neutral ligand (Fig. 1).

PBPAAP

Fig. 1

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes of PBPAAP

Complex	Colour	Analytical data (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Metal	C	H	N	S		
[Cu(PBPAAP)(Cl) ₂]	Reddish brown	12.01 (12.18)	38.98 (39.13)	2.75 (2.87)	10.52 (10.74)	–	5.5	1.79
[Cu(PBPAAP)(CH ₃ COO) ₂]	Brown	11.07 (11.18)	39.93 (40.11)	3.00 (3.16)	9.60 (9.85)	–	1.2	1.79
[Cu(PBPAAP)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown	10.91 (11.06)	35.47 (35.51)	2.59 (2.61)	14.50 (14.62)	–	3.3	1.82
[Cu(PBPAAP)(SO ₄)]	Brown	11.54 (11.62)	37.02 (37.32)	2.62 (2.74)	10.13 (10.25)	5.79 (5.86)	4.5	1.85
[Cu(PBPAAP)(ClO ₄) ₂]	Darkish brown	9.61 (9.78)	31.23 (31.42)	2.12 (2.31)	8.38 (8.62)	–	8.6	1.83
[Cu(PBPAAP)(NCS)(Cl)]	Brown	11.69 (11.70)	39.59 (39.70)	2.73 (2.75)	12.70 (12.87)	5.75 (5.89)	3.8	1.82

Results and discussion

The analytical and spectroscopic data (Tables 1 and 2) showed that all the complexes have the general formula [CuL(X)₂], where L = PBPAAP and X = Cl, NO₃, CH₃COO, ClO₄ or SO₄/2 except for the thiocyanate complex whose composition is [Cu(PBPAAP)(NCS)(Cl)]. The molar conductance values of the complexes measured for 10⁻³ M solutions in nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and methanol (Table 1) adequately confirm the non-electrolytic nature of the metal complexes⁷. The magnetic moments (Table 1) of all the Cu^{II} complexes under the present study are found to be in the range 1.79–1.85 B.M. at room temperature. All the complexes are deeply coloured, non-hygroscopic, stable in air and crystalline. They are soluble in methanol and ethanol, partially soluble in benzene and insoluble in ether. Table 2 lists selected vibrational bands and assignments of ligands and their metal complexes. The infrared spectrum of PBPAAP exhibits a broad

medium intensity band ~3144 cm⁻¹, which indicates the presence of hydrogen bonded -OH group⁸. In the spectra of all the copper complexes of PBPAAP, this band disappears and a new band is observed ~3400 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of free -OH group. This clearly shows that the hydrogen bond is broken during complexation and hence its non-participation in coordination. The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ (azo group) observed ~1639 cm⁻¹ and ~1447 cm⁻¹ respectively in the spectra of the ligands show a downward shift to ~1601 cm⁻¹ and 1407 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes. These are suggestive of the participation of the pyrazol-carbonyl and azo groups in coordination. Thus the ligand exhibit a neutral bidentate behaviour in all the complexes coordinating through the >C=O and -N=N- groups only. All the complexes under the present investigation show weak intensity bands ~504 cm⁻¹ and ~436 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Cu-O}}$ respectively⁹.

Table 2. Spectral data of the ligand PBPAAP and its copper(II) complexes

Ligand/Complexes	Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)					
	ν_{OH} (hydrogen bonded)	ν_{OH} (free)	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{N=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Cu-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{Cu-O}}$
PBPAAP	3144	–	1639	1447	–	–
[Cu(PBPAAP)(Cl) ₂]	–	3423	1613	1407	512	460
[Cu(PBPAAP)(NO ₃) ₂]	–	3422	1604	1403	504	436
[Cu(PBPAAP)(CH ₃ COO) ₂]	–	3409	1607	1397	499	450
[Cu(PBPAAP)(SO ₄)]	–	3416	1601	1407	499	440
[Cu(PBPAAP)(ClO ₄) ₂]	–	3376	1613	1392	499	440
[Cu(PBPAAP)(NCS)(Cl)]	–	3163	1606	1406	507	460

Fig. 2. TG and DTG curves of $[\text{Cu}(\text{PBPAAP})(\text{Cl})_2]$

For the perchlorate complex, ν_3 and ν_4 appear as strong and medium intensity bands $\sim 691 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1140 cm^{-1} respectively, indicating a monodentately coordinated perchlorate group. The medium intensity band observed $\sim 837 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2) in the spectra of the perchlorate complexes confirms this fully¹⁰.

The *N*-coordinated nature of the thiocyanate group¹¹ is indicated by the $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ ($\sim 2081 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ ($\sim 763 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and ν_{NCS} ($\sim 507 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands. The bands $\sim 1490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_4) and $\sim 1294 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_1) with a separation of about 196 cm^{-1} are suggestive of monodentately coordinated nitrate group¹².

Acetate complex exhibit a strong band $\sim 1586 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and medium intensity band $\sim 1346 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which can be attributed to $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ respectively of acetate group. The position of these vibrations and their separation by 240 cm^{-1} are as seen for unidentate coordination of acetate group¹³.

Regarding sulphate complex, the infrared spectral bands $\sim 1228 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 1169 cm^{-1} and 1075 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_3 of chelating bidentate sulphate group¹⁴.

The electronic spectra of copper(II) complexes in methanol exhibit bands $\sim 245 \text{ nm}$, 388 nm , 428 nm and 695 nm . The first two are assigned to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The band at 428 nm is assigned to charge transfer transition and the other at 695 nm is attributed to

d-d transition (${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$). Thus, the electronic spectral data suggest D_{4h} symmetry for the complexes¹⁵.

In the ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra¹⁶ of the ligand PBPAAP, the signals due to two methyl protons are observed in the region $\delta 2.17\text{--}2.68 \text{ ppm}$ and $\delta 2.85\text{--}3.38 \text{ ppm}$. The latter may be that due to the *N*-methyl protons. The signal due to five aromatic protons of the antipyrine phenyl ring appeared as a multiplet between $\delta 6.85\text{--}7.58 \text{ ppm}$. The phenolic proton signal is observed as a singlet at $\delta 7.79 \text{ ppm}$.

The thermogravimetric curve of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{PBPAAP})(\text{Cl})_2]$ was recorded in the temperature range ambient to $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, in an atmosphere of nitrogen (Fig. 2). The TG and DTG curves do not show the presence of water molecule and the complex is stable upto $140 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The decomposition of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{PBPAAP})(\text{Cl})_2]$ occur in two stages. The first stage of decomposition in the TG curve is from 140 to $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ which corresponds to elimination of the anionic part. During the second decomposition stage ($460\text{--}730 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) the ligand part gets eliminated. The final mass loss observed agrees with the values calculated for the conversion of the complex into metallic copper. The order parameter for the two stages of decomposition are two. The energy of activation for the first stage of decomposition is found to be $80.36 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and that for

the second stage of decomposition is $107.40 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. The values of ΔS for the two stages of decomposition are $-173.83 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ and $-159.52 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively¹⁷.

Table 3. X-Ray diffraction data of [Cu(PBPAAP)(NCS)(Cl)]

Line	<i>hkl</i>	$\sin^2 \theta$ (Obsd.)	$\sin^2 \theta$ (Calcd.)	Relative intensity (%)
1	100	0.0120	0.0114	52.81
2	002	0.0156	0.0148	33.97
3	012	0.0197	0.0210	91.10
4	021	0.0297	0.0285	51.03
5	003	0.0334	0.0333	100.00
6	013	0.0396	0.0395	94.19
7	103	0.0446	0.0447	47.17
8	201	0.0481	0.0493	72.42
9	211	0.0555	0.0555	63.48
10	031	0.0596	0.0595	56.48
11	014	0.0657	0.0654	52.69
12	123	0.0693	0.0695	49.88
13	300	0.1027	0.1026	26.78
14	242	0.1585	0.1596	17.36

The X-ray diffraction studies of the complex [Cu(PBPAAP)(NCS)(Cl)] have been carried out (Fig. 3) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405 \text{ \AA}$. The diffraction patterns of the complex recorded 14 reflections between 2θ ranging from 10° to 50° with maxima at $2\theta = 46.926$ which corresponds to $d = 1.9345 \text{ \AA}$. The main peaks have been indexed (Table 3) using Hesse and Lipson's procedure^{18,19}. The observed values fit well with orthorhombic system to give a unit cell with dimensions : $a = 7.2117 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.7790 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 12.6587 \text{ \AA}$.

The X-band ESR spectra of the complex (Fig. 4) [Cu(PBPAAP)(Ac)₂] was recorded at room temperature in solid state (polycrystalline form). Hyperfine splitting into four lines with partial overlap [$I = 3/2$ for Cu^{II}] is seen in the parallel component of [Cu(PBPAAP)(Ac)₂]. The ESR parameters g_{\parallel} , $g_{\perp r}$, g_{av} calculated are 2.20, 2.03 and 2.08 respectively²⁰. The trends $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp r} > g_e$ (free ion value = 2.0036) observed for this complex shows that the unpaired electron is localized in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of Cu^{II} ion and the spectrum is characteristic of axial symmetry. The A_{\parallel} value for the complex calculated is 104 G. Since the $\perp r$ component shows no hyperfine split, $A_{\perp r} = 0$.

Fig. 3. X-Ray diffraction pattern of [Cu(PBPAAP)(NCS)(Cl)].

Fig. 4. ESR spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{PBPAAP})(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2]$

On the basis of the above physicochemical studies, a square planar geometry (Fig. 5) has been tentatively proposed for all the copper(II) complexes.

$\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{NO}_3, \text{ClO}_4, \text{CH}_3\text{COO}, \text{SO}_4/2$
 $[\text{Cu}(\text{PBPAAP})(\text{X})_2]$

$[\text{Cu}(\text{PBPAAP})(\text{NCS})(\text{Cl})]$

Fig. 5. Suggested structures for the Cu^{II} complexes of PBPAAP

Experimental

4-Aminoantipyrine (E. Merck, Germany), *p*-bromophenol (Sisco, Mumbai), copper(II) acetate and copper(II) sulphate (B.D.H., England) were used as such. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Metal, halide and sulphur in the complexes were estimated by standard methods²¹. Perchlorate was estimated by Kurz's method²². Elemental analysis (C, H and N) of the complexes were carried out at Sophisticated Test and Instrumentation Centre (STIC), Cochin, Kerala. The IR spectra were recorded in the $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region on a JASCO FTIR 430 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded in methanol with JASCO V550 UV-Vis spectrophotometer in the range $900\text{--}200\text{ nm}$. ^1H NMR spectrum was recorded in CDCl_3 on 300 MHz (Bruker Advance dpx-300) FT-NMR spectrometer using TMS as reference material. The molar conductances of the complexes in $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NO}_2$, CH_3OH and CH_3CN (*ca.* 10^{-3} M) were measured at $(300 \pm 2\text{ K})$ using an Elico conductivity bridge type CM 82T with a dip type cell (ec-03) fitted with platinum electrodes (cell constant is 0.94 cm^{-1}). Magnetic susceptibilities at room temperature ($300 \pm 2\text{ K}$) were measured on a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The X-ray powder diffraction patterns were obtained on Philips X-ray diffractometer (PW 1710) using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation with $\lambda = 1.5405\text{ \AA}$. Thermogravimetric curves of complexes were recorded on a Mettler Toledo STARE thermal analysis system, consisting of STARE software with a heating rate of $10\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ in an atmosphere of nitrogen in platinum crucible in the temperature range $0\text{--}800\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. ESR spectra of the complex was recorded on a Varian E-112 X-Q band spectrometer with DPPH as reference material.

Synthesis of ligand : The ligand PBPAAP was synthesized from 4-aminoantipyrine and *p*-bromophenol by diazotization and coupling as described in the literature²³.

Synthesis of copper(II) complexes : All except the thiocyanate complex were prepared by the following general method. Hot methanolic solutions of metal salts (2.5 mmol) were added to hot methanolic solutions of the ligand (2.5 mmol) and refluxed for about 5–6 h. The complexes obtained on volume reduction were filtered, washed with aqueous methanol followed by dry ether and then dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo*. Yield is about 60–70%.

For preparing thiocyanate complex, about 0.5 g of NH_4SCN was added to a methanolic solution of the metal chloride (2.5 mmol), stirred well and filtered. The filtrate was then refluxed with a hot methanolic solution of the ligand (2.5 mmol) for nearly 5 h. The solid separated on concentration of the solution was then filtered, washed with aqueous methanol followed by dry ether and then dried over P_4O_{10} *in vacuo*. Yield 65%.

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